

USE OF EXPANDABLE MULTI-LAYER METAL LAMINATES AS FIRE PROTECTION FOR ALUMINIUM AND CFRP AEROSPACES STRUCTURES

S. Christke¹, G. Gibson¹, S. Wan-Jusoh¹, G. Kotsikos¹ and A. Mouritz²

¹School of Mechanical and Systems Engineering, Newcastle University, Newcastle upon Tyne, NE1
7RU, United Kingdom

Email: s.christke@ncl.ac.uk, web page: <http://www.ncl.ac.uk/mech>

²School of Aerospace, Mechanical and Manufacturing Engineering, RMIT University, Melbourne,
GPO Box 2476, VIC 3001, Australia

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ABSTRACT

Their relatively poor fire performance under load is a significant drawback for both aluminium and composite structures. Exposed to significant heat flux, aluminium in tension or compression fails by a combination of yield and creep. Carbon composite structures behave well in tension but poorly in compression, where their behaviour is limited by the resin reaching its glass transition temperature. None of the accepted means of fire protection is viable in case of external surfaces of aerospace structures. Passive fire protective coatings, including intumescent, would be unsightly and unlikely to survive flight conditions. Furthermore, these coatings are parasitic as they contribute to the weight of the structure without improving its strength.

One attractive solution is the use of multi-layer metal laminates, bonded to the exterior of the structure. Such laminates are weight-effective and do not detract from appearance. Exposed to high temperatures these laminates will debond, producing a multi-layer expanded structure of low thermal conductivity which limits the heat flux passing into the substrate.

This paper reports a study of the use of 10- and 20-layer thick aluminium/epoxy laminates to protect aluminium plates and carbon/epoxy laminates. The protection layers were 30 micron thick foils, separated by 10micron layers of epoxy resin. Both the aluminium and the CFRP substrates were 6.35mm thick. 100mm by 50mm regions of the protected surface were subjected to a 50kW/m² radiant heat flux. The substrates were clamped in the grips of a testing machine and loaded at a defined fraction of the room temperature failure load.

The effect of the fire protection was to significantly reduce the temperature reached in the aluminium and CFRP specimens. Stress-rupture relationships in fire are reported for both sample types in the form of curves of failure time vs. stress. These show considerable improvements in the fire durability of the systems examined.

1 INTRODUCTION

Aluminium alloys and fibre-reinforced polymeric composites are the preferred choice of materials for aerospace applications due to their structural performance whilst offering lightweight construction [1-5]. A significant drawback for both aluminium and composite structures is, however, their relatively poor performance under load in fire. When subjected to significant heat flux, aluminium alloys rapidly fail under load in either tension or compression via a combination of yield and creep due to the surpassing of the material's softening points at relatively low temperatures [6-9]. Carbon-fibre reinforced composite structures, on the other hand, behave well in tension but poorly in compression, where their behaviour is limited by the polymeric matrix reaching its glass transition temperature, which is usually around 200°C [10,11]. While it would be desirable to protect such structures from heat flux in use, none of the accepted means of fire protection is viable in the case of the external surfaces of aerospace structures. Passive fire protective coatings, including intumescent, would be both unsightly and unlikely to survive flight conditions. Furthermore, these coatings are parasitic as

they contribute to the weight of the structure without improving its strength.

This paper reports on multi-layer metal laminates as a novel fire protection method for use on aerospace structures. An experimental investigation is presented showing the fire protection efficacy of these metal laminates by means of structural testing of aluminium and carbon/epoxy structures under tensile as well as compressive loading whilst exposed to radiant heat flux.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials and sample preparation

A 6.35mm thick 2024-T351 aluminium alloy plate was cut down into strips of 600mm length and 50mm width with the longer direction corresponding to the rolling direction of the material. The cold-rolled samples showed a slight initial curvature of up to 0.2mm which is due to the residual stresses induced during the forming process.

The composite material has been manufactured from unidirectional Carbon/Epoxy prepreg of type AS4/3501-6 supplied by Hexcel. The individual plies were arranged in a symmetric and balanced stacking order to construct a quasi-isotropic composite material featuring a [0/45/90/-45] lay-up with a similar thickness to the aluminium alloy specimens. The manufactured composite sheets were cut down via a water jet cutting process into strips of 600mm length and 50mm width with the longer direction corresponding to the 0° ply orientation of the laminate.

Two types of metal laminates have been tested as thermal barrier. The thin aluminium-epoxy laminate is comprised of 10 layers of 30µm thick aluminium foil separated by several micrometre thick layers of epoxy resin which results in a total laminate thickness of around 0.4mm. The thicker metal laminate is doubled up to 20 layers. In preparation for testing, strips of these laminates were bonded onto the front of aluminium alloy and carbon/epoxy specimens.

Samples featuring metal laminates as well as the unprotected aluminium specimens were spray-painted with heat-resistant black paint which maximises the heat transfer into the sample during the fire exposure. Ceramic fibre blanket as thermal insulation was wrapped around all edges leaving only a 100mm long window open at the front. For samples with a laminate top layer, bulldog clips were used to apply pressure on the edges in order to avoid undesirable delamination of the laminate at the edges.

2.2 Fire structural testing

A 250kN load capacity MTS machine was used to determine the material's tensile and compressive behaviour under the influence of one-sided heating. The samples were clamped on both ends in such way that the load is applied parallel to the rolling direction of the aluminium alloy and parallel to the 0° ply of the composite, leaving a free gauge length of 430mm. Only a small 100x50mm² section at the centre of the sample was exposed to a constant radiant heat from a 15cm diameter coil heater. The rest of the sample was thermally insulated in order to induce the localised heating at the sample centre as well as to avoid overheating of the machine grips. K-type thermocouples attached to the front and the back face of the sample monitored the temperature development during the actual test. Additionally for compression testing, a LVDT device with a maximum gauge length of 8mm was used to measure the horizontal displacement of the centre point at the back face.

During the fire-structural test a constant load was applied to the specimen while it was exposed to one-sided heating of 50kW/m² from the radiant heat source. Applied load levels ranged from 90% to 5% of the room temperature strength. For the tensile tests the applied force was based on the material's yield strength in case of aluminium (347MPa) and tensile failure strength in case of the composite (588MPa). The axial extension of a sample was measured using the machine's cross-head displacement. Load levels for the compression tests were based on the Euler buckling stress of either material (39MPa for aluminium and 24MPa for CFRP). Again, in-plane deformation of the sample was measured using the machine's cross-head displacement whereas the out-of-plane displacement was additionally monitored via LVDT.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Temperature curves

Exemplary curves of specimens' back face temperatures recorded during fire-structural testing at 50kW/m^2 are shown in Fig. 1. A dependency on the type of loading or tested without load applied has not been observed. The temperature reduction due to the introduction of the metal laminates as thermal barriers is clearly noticeable.

Unprotected aluminium alloy specimens initially experience an almost linear temperature increase before steady-state conditions are reached at around 330°C . Specimens featuring metal laminates display a much slower heating up rate as the fire protection effect of the insulation is developing. The 20-layer laminate provides an improved insulation effect compared to the thinner laminate as a further reduction of the initial heating up rate can be observed before specimens with both types of thermal barrier stabilise at a temperature of around 50°C and 60°C lower than the unprotected AA2024 (at 1 hour of testing).

In contrast to the aluminium, pristine CFRP specimens experience a steady increase in back face temperature with no steady-state conditions developing. As a combustible material, thermal degradation plays an important role when temperatures are high enough and the material's decomposition temperature is exceeded. The endothermic decomposition reactions in combination with the released volatile gases and the on-going exposure to the radiant heat source are contributing to the steady rise in temperature. At temperatures above 600°C most of the organic matrix has been transformed into char and combustibles and degradation of the carbon fibres is initiated.

Figure 1: Temperature curves recorded during fire-structural testing whilst exposed to a heat flux of 50kW/m^2 . Samples tested were a) unprotected AA2024 substrates and b) CFRP laminates as well as same type specimens featuring metal laminates of either 10 or 20 layers.

CFRP specimens insulated featuring metal laminates exhibit a similar initial reduction in heating rate as the insulated AA2024 specimens. The onset of the matrix's decomposition cannot be suppressed although it is initiated at a much later point due to the delay in heat transfer into the substrate material. However, the unceasing increase in temperature as seen with the unprotected composite specimens is repressed due to the insulation effect of the laminates. Maximum temperatures of 450°C are recorded before steady-state conditions develop at around 420°C . Similar to the above section, specimens featuring the thicker laminate show a slightly slower heating up rate in the initial phase than the 10-layer laminate before stable temperatures are reached.

A clear distinction to the aluminium alloy becomes very obvious as not just a shift to lower temperatures is observed, as seen in the metal specimens, but the insulation also contributes to a change in temperature behaviour in combustible materials.

3.2 Proof of expansion

The insulation effect of the laminates arises from the release and enclosure of decomposition gases of the polymer layers within the laminate during fire exposure. Fig. 2a shows a micrograph of an expanded laminate that has been taken from a fire-structural test specimen after it had been exposed to 50kW/m^2 for a short time period. The top of the picture represents the hot face of the specimen that has been exposed to the heat whereas the bottom of the picture correlates to the interface section towards the cooler substrate material. A clear delamination of the aluminium layers is visible demonstrating the formation of gas-filled pockets during heat exposure.

Fig. 2b presents the expansion behaviour of coupon-sized ($50\times 60\text{mm}^2$) polymer-laminate samples obtained from isothermal furnace testing over a wide temperature range. At lower temperature ranges the observed expansion is solely due to thermal expansion as temperatures are not high enough to induce decomposition. After the polymer's decomposition temperature is exceeded swelling of the laminates occurs with an average maximum expansion of around 9. The curve for 500°C shows a decline in expansion after reaching its maximum. This is associated with the loss of some of the decomposition gases as the forming gas pockets reach the edges of the samples.

Figure 2: Expansion behaviour of metal laminates during heat exposure, a) micrograph of fire-structural test sample after 1h heat exposure, b) expansion factor obtained via isothermal furnace tests

3.3 Displacement curves

The plots of the recorded displacement parallel to the loading direction show in general an increase in plastic deformation before failure when multi-layer metal laminates are used as thermal barriers.

For AA2024 specimens in tension testing, the initial in-plane displacement can be attributed to the thermal expansion of the metal. This is followed by a sharp increase in the deformation rate leading to abrupt plastic failure of the specimens indicating the presence of much higher forces within the sample than the instantaneous elevated yield strength of the material. Insulated samples experience a decrease in the displacement rate after the initial thermal expansion period which leads to extended times before abrupt failure occurs. This creep-like behaviour is most pronounced in specimens featuring the thicker metal laminate where lower temperatures denote higher instantaneous yield strength within AA2024 which leads to extended failure times and increased axial displacement.

Similar principles apply for AA2024 under compression loading where thermal expansion causes the initial axial displacement before a maximum point is reached which is associated with the onset of plastic failure. As the axial extension decreases, the out-of-plane deformation increases sharply resulting in the buckling of the aluminium sample. The lower temperatures in insulated specimens again lead to increased deformation in both axes before final failure occurs.

Figure 3: Comparison of in-plane displacement between unprotected AA2024 and aluminium alloy substrates featuring a 10- or 20-layer metal laminate, tested under a) tension and b) compression during heat exposure.

Due to the brittle nature of CFRP composites, specimens tested under tension or compression show little extension before rapid failure occurs. In compression, samples exhibit very little in-plane as well as out-of-plane deformation. Failure occurs as localized buckling which is accompanied by the formation of a kink band. In tension the effect of the insulation onto the failure behaviour becomes prominent. The progressive thermal damage in unprotected specimens leads to rapid failure as the applied load can no longer be supported. Insulated samples, in contrast, exhibit very different behaviour. Due to the lower temperatures the thermal degradation of the material is not as advanced so that fibres are mainly intact having high residual strength and can support the applied tensile load resulting in extended failure times and increased axial displacement.

Figure 4: Comparison of in-plane displacement between unprotected CFRP substrates CFRP laminates featuring a 10- or 20-layer metal laminate, tested under a) tension and b) compression during heat exposure.

3.4 Failure times

Time-to-failure (TTF) plots for fire-structural testing under tension and compression loading are shown in Fig. 5 and 6. In general, the failure times decrease with a rise in the applied load. The experimental data points describe the boundary line below which specimens are deemed to be safe, above that samples will fail. During the testing, when the applied load fell below a certain level some of the specimens would not fail and the fire-structural tests were consequently stopped after two hours.

These run-outs are included into the TTF curves as set points positioned at 7200 seconds although they do not represent the true failure time.

Recorded TTF curves of AA2024 samples show the expected typical decaying behaviour. They exhibit an initial rapid decrease in failure times with a reduction from high to lower load levels before extended failure times can be noticed at low load levels. For compression testing run-outs occur below 30% of the applied load; in tension mode this appears at 5% load level.

Different failure modes can be observed for the CFRP specimens depending on the loading condition. For compression the failure is matrix dominated which means that failure occurs rapidly due to softening and decomposition. Only a slight increase in failure times with decrease in load is found as the residual strength of the softened epoxy matrix is not able to support low loads. For specimens tested under tension, failure is fibre dominated. After the matrix has softened the residual fibre strength is high enough to provide strength at low load levels. Final failure occurs there as a result of the continuous heat input over an extended time period as the temperatures within material exceed the onset of fibre degradation, which eventually causes the specimen to fail when the strength is reduced below the applied load level. With this progressive degradation of the composite material no run-outs are observed for unprotected CFRP specimens.

Figure 5: Failure times for pristine AA2024 and metal laminate protected AA2024 samples tested under a) tensile and b) compressive loading whilst exposed to 50kW/m^2 heat flux.

The plots show the material's sensitivity to the imposed loading condition. The CFRP samples are susceptible to compressive loading, whereas AA2024 specimens can withstand compression better than tension. The failure mode visually changes depending on the load applied as the affected heating zone spreads over the specimen with prolonged exposure time. For AA2024 the abrupt tensile failure at high load becomes a pronounced deformation (necking) before failure at low loads. In compression, increased out-of-plane deformation can be noticed. In case of CFRP samples, brittle tensile failure changes to resin depleted fibre failure. An increase in the size of the formed kink band is observed for specimens tested under compressive loading.

As expected, specimens featuring the developed metal laminates display increased failure times during fire-structural testing due to the thermal shielding effect of the insulation. Also, samples with the 20-layer laminate show longer failure times than the ones with the thinner laminate. This is caused by the greater insulation effect created in the thicker laminate which provides a more effective way of prolonging the heat transfer into the underlying substrate material.

For insulated AA2024 specimens, TTF curves similar in shape to the unprotected AA2024 are found. In tension testing no failure of samples is observed at 30% or 40% load level (depending on laminate type) which is in contrast to the unprotected aluminium where run-outs are only observed as low as 5%. A minimum improvement in failure time by factor of around 2 can be achieved due to the introduction of the metal laminates. This factor increases hugely with a reduction in load level. Similar conclusions can be made for insulated AA2024 under compression loading where run-outs occur at 50% and 60% applied load.

Figure 6: Failure times for pristine CFRP and metal laminate protected CFRP samples tested under a) tensile and b) compressive loading whilst exposed to 50kW/m² heat flux.

Again, improved failure times are measured for insulated CFRP specimens as a similar insulation effect is observed as with the AA2024 samples. It also applies that the thicker laminate provides a greater thermal barrier. A slight behaviour change can be noticed as those samples with the 20-layer laminate initially experience lower temperatures leading to longer failure times compared to the 10-layer laminated samples. However, with ongoing test time the temperatures within the two different sample types stabilise around the same temperature level, as could be seen from the temperature profile in above section, providing similar shielding effect. The result is similar failure times at low loads which is most pronounced in the converging of the TTF curves for compression loading with decreasing load levels.

In fire-structural tests under tension the consequence of the laminates' insulation effect becomes even more apparent. At lower load levels where the thermal degradation of the composite plays an important role in its failure behaviour due to prolonged exposure times, insulated samples show hugely extended failure times. The metal laminates do not prevent matrix softening or decomposition but the maximum temperatures reached are found to be below temperatures where fibre oxidation occurs which is the main cause of failure in unprotected CFRP specimens. As a result no specimen failure occurs below 40% applied load for insulated samples whereas run-outs in pristine CFRP even as low as 10% load could not be observed.

4 CONCLUSIONS

This study has shown that novel multi-layer metal laminates present a viable alternative to traditional fire protection methods.

The concept of expandable metal laminates through entrapment of decomposition gases is established. A multiplicity of interfaces with low thermal conductivity is cause for the observed insulation effect.

During the fire-structural testing of aluminium and CFRP, a significant reduction in the temperatures is reached in both aluminium and CFRP specimens in comparison to unprotected specimens due to the introduction of metal laminates. Due to lower specimen temperature considerable improvements in the fire durability of the systems examined can be achieved as failure times under various loading conditions are greatly extended.

REFERENCES

- [1] T. Dursun and C. Soutis, Recent developments in advanced aircraft aluminium alloys. *Materials & Design*, **56**, 2014, pp. 862–871.

- [2] J-P. Immarigeon, R.T. Holt, A.K. Koul, L. Zhao, W. Wallace, and J.C. Beddoes, Lightweight materials for aircraft applications. *Materials Characterization*, 35, 1995, pp. 41–67.
- [3] J.C. Williams and E.A. Starke, Progress in structural materials for aerospace systems, *Acta Materialia*, 51, 2003, pp. 5775–5799.
- [4] W.T. Freeman, The use of composites in aircraft primary structure, *Composites Engineering*, 3, 1993, pp. 767–775.
- [5] C. Soutis. Carbon fiber reinforced plastics in aircraft construction. *Materials Science and Engineering: A*, 412, 2005, pp. 171–176.
- [6] B. Faggiano, G. De Matteis, R. Landolfo, and F.M. Mazzolani, Behaviour of aluminium alloy structures under fire, *Journal of Civil Engineering and Management*, 10, 2004, pp. 183–190.
- [7] J. Maljaars, F. Soetens, and H.H. Snijder, Local buckling of aluminium structures exposed to fire Part 1: Tests, *Thin-Walled Structures*, 47, 2009, pp. 1404–1417.
- [8] E.J. Fogle, B.Y. Lattimer, S. Feih, E. Kandare, A.P. Mouritz, and S.W. Case, Compression load failure of aluminum plates due to fire, *Engineering Structures*, 34, 2012, pp. 155–162.
- [9] A. Afaghi Khatibi, E. Kandare, S. Feih, B.Y. Lattimer, S.W. Case, and A.P. Mouritz, Finite Element modelling of tensile deformation and failure of aluminium plate exposed to fire, *Computational Materials Science*, 95, 2014, pp. 242–249.
- [10] L.A. Burns, S. Feih, A.P. Mouritz, Compression failure of carbon fiber-epoxy laminates in fire, *Journal of Aircraft*, 47, 2010, pp. 528–533.
- [11] S. Feih, A.P. Mouritz, Tensile properties of carbon fibres and carbon fibre-polymer composites in fire, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, 43, 2012, pp. 765–772.